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ESSENCE OF CLOUD COMPUTING IN LIBRARIES

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ESSENCE OF CLOUD COMPUTING IN LIBRARIES

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing is a new technology model for Information Technology (IT) services which is extensively used in today industry as well as society. Cloud computing brings the revolutionary changes in the world of Information Communication Technology (ICT) because of its potential benefits such as reduced cost, accessible anywhere anytime as well as its elasticity and flexibility. This paper defines cloud computing and how cloud computing solutions cloud be beneficial to libraries.

Keywords: ICT, Cloud Computing, Types of Cloud, Libraries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing can transform the way systems are built and services delivered, providing libraries with an opportunity to extend their impact. Cloud computing has become a major topic of discussion and debate for any business or organization, which relies on technology. Anyone connected to the Internet is probably using some type of cloud computing on a regular basis. Whether they are using Google's Gmail, organizing photos on Flickr or searching the Web with Bing they are engaged in cloud computing. As Geoffrey Moore points out, the interesting thing about cloud computing is it did not start as a technology for the business enterprise, but was driven by the public with services like Facebook and Flickr. The purpose of this article is to look specifically at how cloud computing can be employed by libraries.

2. WHAT IS CLOUD COMPUTING?

Cloud computing can be understood as a way to use off-site computer processing power to replace content creation and servers that were traditionally hosted onsite. In layman's terms this means "using Web services for out computing needs" (Kroski, 2009). Cloud computer allows content creation to be made "when data and software applications reside on and are drawn from the network rather than locally on any one workstation". By utilizing online applications, users can create and save their files online, share content (often for free!), work collaboratively with

others or create entire services that can all be accessed online without need of having the programs on their own computer. These online services can reduce the need for expensive software, hardware, and even advanced technical knowledge from library staff since cloud computing services are often streamlined to be very user-friendly. As well, "the focus shifts away from which devices effectively store data and able to run applications to which devices can provide the easiest access to data and applications – which are stored at various places on the Internet". The Gartner Group defines cloud computing as "a style of computing in which massively scalable and elastic IT – enabled capabilities are delivered as a service to external customers using Internet technologies". In various presentations there is four different types of cloud computing: infrastructure, platform, applications and services. To put this in more concrete terms, examples of each can be.

The table illustrates why there are varying definitions of cloud computing. Many cloud services actually incorporate two or more of these types. For example, Google docs provide infrastructure as well as applications. It should also be noted that many cloud applications and services are actually using another providers' cloud infrastructure to run their service.

3. TYPES OF CLOUD SERVICES

There are three major types of cloud services available:

Type	What it is	Examples
Services	Ready to use services accessed with a Web Browser	Google Maps
Applications	Software applications accessed with a Web Browser	Google Docs, Microsoft 365, Salesforce.com
Platform	An existing software platform to build your own applications on	Facebook
Infrastructure	Buying space/time on external servers	Amazon A3

- 1. Software as a Service (SaaS) :** Applications or software is delivered as a service to the customer who can access the program from any online device. Some of these Web-based applications are free such as Hotmail, Google, Apps, Skype, and many 2.0 applications, while most business-oriented SaaS, such as SalesForce, is leased on a subscription basis. There is usually little customization or control available with these applications. However, subscribers benefit from low initial costs, have access to (usually 24/7) support services, and needn't worry about hosting, installing, upgrading, or maintaining the software.
- 2. Platform as a Service (PaaS) :** With PaaS, a computing platform is provided which supplies tools and a development environment to help companies build, test, and deploy Web-based applications. Businesses don't need to invest in the infrastructure required for building Web and mobile applications but can rent the use of platforms such as Windows Azure, Google AppEngine, and Force.com. Applications which are built using these provider's services, however, are usually locked into that one platform.
- 3. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) :** This type of cloud computing is also sometimes referred to as HaaS or Hardware as a Service and it involves both storage services and computing power. Amazon's Web Services, one of the major players in this area, offers two main products including the Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2), which provides computing resources, and Simple Storage Service (S3) for data storage. Companies are using Amazon's Web Services to host or backup their websites, for content delivery, to run high performance computing simulations, to host media collections, and much more. Most of these cloud services are available on a pay-per-usage basis, differing from the SaaS subscription model, enabling customers to scale up or down depending on their need at any given time and only pay for what they've used.

4. HOW IS CLOUD COMPUTING DIFFERENT

For much of the past 25 years, software development and system engineering has centered primarily on the personal computer. The PC era was characterized by monolithic, proprietary operating systems and programs that had long development times and release cycles. In that environment, the design of software was isolated and all attention focused

on a single application. With cloud computing, hardware and functionality traditionally installed and run in an local environment is now performed on the network, in the Internet cloud. In essence, the Internet cloud becomes the development platform and the operating system to which programmers write reusable, constantly updated software components that are delivered over the network and that can be embedded or loosely coupled with other Web applications. Libraries have been using some cloud computing services for over a decade. Online databases are accessed as cloud applications. Large union catalogs can also be defined as cloud applications.

5. LIBRARIES AND THE CLOUD

Libraries are also not left blank with the emerging technology i.e. cloud computing. Many enterprises are implementing cloud computing as a new technology model for ICT infrastructures and services. Cloud computing allows libraries to avoid locally hosting multiple servers and equipment and constantly deals with hardware failure, software installs, upgrades and compatibility issues and this is possible because processes get simplified and libraries save time and money. ICT related headaches of libraries get reduced by the introduction of this technology. Furthermore it can concurrently make workflows simpler and permit the libraries to make available improved end-user customer services with highly developed library find means and assist them online through a large network of collaborating librarians globally.

6. WHAT CAN CLOUD COMPUTING SOLUTIONS DO FOR LIBRARIES

Turning to cloud computing and libraries, are their real problems that can solved? The answer is yes. The library community can apply the concept of cloud computing to amplify the power of cooperation and to build a significant, unified presence on the Web. This approach to computing can help libraries save time and money while simplifying workflows.

A brief list of potential areas of improvement could include:

- Most library computer systems are built on pre-Web technology;
- Systems distributed across the Net using pre-Web technology are harder and more costly to integrate;
- Libraries store and maintain much of the same data

- hundreds and thousands of times;
- d) With library data scatter across distributed systems the library's Web presence is weakened;
- e) With libraries running independent systems collaboration between libraries is made difficult and expensive;
- f) Information seekers work in common Web environments and distributed systems make it difficult to get the library into their workflow; and
- g) Many systems are only used to 10% of their capacity. Combining systems into a cloud environment reduces the carbon footprints, making libraries greener.

7. REAL WORLD EXAMPLE OF CURRENT LIBRARY CLOUD

- 7.1 **OCLC** : Online Computer Library Center (OCLC) is a nonprofit, membership, computer library services and research organization dedicated to the public purposes of furthering access to the world's information and reducing the rate of rise of library costs. In a sense OCLC has been functioning as a cloud computing vendor. They provide cataloguing tools over the Internet and allow member institution to draw on their centralized data store. This centralized database allows for the sharing of catalog records between libraries and greatly reduces the time spent in cataloging incoming material. World Cat is another example of cloud computing architecture drawing on the union catalog infrastructure they have built up over the years.
- 7.2 **LIBRARY THING**: It is one of the sites that combine aspects of social networking and cloud computing is Library Thing, originator of which is Tim Spalding. Library Thing offers services which are just like social networking site, authorizes people to contribute information and suggestion about books and allows them to interconnect globally to share interests. This site also contributes Web services for libraries after paying a nominal fee it allows libraries to draw on the vast database of recommendation and other users available in Library Thing.
- 7.3 **REED ELSEVIER**: Reed Elsevier is a service provider for scientific information working with hospitals to provide point in time information to medical technicians, as they need the information. It is capitalizing on the cloud computing model. There is the possibility to place monographic and article content or even technical manuals so that technician and other medical personnel can get assistance exactly when they need it. This utilizes the cloud computing model in the way that computers and others devices used in the medical profession can be tied into the data and application provided by the Elsevier from anywhere.

- 7.4 **AMAZON AND GOOGLE**: These are among the leading enterprises also providing solutions for libraries by having partnerships between library automation vendors. Amazon has been developing for years a large Web services architecture and they now offer hosting services for data which are priced at gigabytes-month and CPU hour rates. We basically pay what we actually use. Google for years is working for the dissemination of information also taking interest in library solutions, going to implement "APP Engine" which provides a hosted services for application within their server farms and on massive and highly redundant storage system. IBM are showing curiosity in the world and has begun developing an infrastructure known by the name BLUE CLOUD.
- 7.5 **KINDLE**: In the electronic book arena Amazon is providing some reading services with Kindle. It one have wireless connection, can purchase and read a rapidly growing list of books and periodicals from the Kindle no matter for the location. With these services largest text can be downloaded in seconds.
- 7.6 **DURASPACE**: A hosted services and open technology to help organizations and end users effectively utilize public cloud services. Built upon existing cloud services. The service can work on Amazon, Atmos, Sun Rackspace, and other cloud services LOCKSS in the cloud based on DuraCloud.
- 7.7 **CHRONOPOLIS PROJECT**: Designed primarily as a preservation storage system. Chronopolis tools also monitors file and does auditing.
- 7.8 **TERRAPOD**: ADigital video library. It allows to outsource upload and data creation to the creators of the content.

8. CONCLUSION

Libraries have the opportunity to improve their services and relevance in today's information society. Cloud computing is one avenue for this move into the future. It can bring several benefits for the libraries and give them a different future. The cloud computing model will encourage libraries and their users to participate in a network and community of libraries by enabling them to reuse information and socialize around information. It can also create a powerful, unified presence for libraries on the web and give users a local, group and global reach.

It is an entirely new form of computing which many enterprises such as Google, Yahoo, Microsoft, Amazon, Zoho and sales force are adopting for infrastructure solutions. Cloud computing is attracting enterprises and now libraries due to number of reasons. The concept is that it shifts the bulk of the responsibility for infrastructure

support out to another vendor and basically outsource all data centers and software support to a company that specializes in web-based computing.

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